

Mass Spectrometry as a Diagnostic Tool for Alzheimer's Biomarkers in Cerebrospinal Fluid

August 30, 2025

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Abstract

Alzheimer's disease is one of the most severe disorders in adults, as it causes memory loss and difficulties in performing daily activities. It imposes a financial, emotional, and social burden on both the patient and their family. The aim of this study is to evaluate mass spectrometry for the early diagnosis of Alzheimer's biomarkers A β 1-40/A β 1-42 and tau protein in cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) samples. This technique proves to be important, as it provides rapid and reliable results in combination with liquid chromatography (LC) for the early assessment of the presence of the pathology. However, it is not yet established for evaluating disease severity or monitoring patient response to therapy.

I. Introduction

Alzheimer's disease is characterized by a progressive loss of neurons. Specifically, solid extracellular amyloid-beta (A β) plaques accumulate and neurofibrillary tangles formed by tau protein develop around brain nerve cells.

It is one of the most important health problems in adults, as it is incurable and fatal. In 2006, 26.6 million people worldwide were reported to be affected, and this number is expected to triple by 2050.

Its main symptoms are:

- memory and judgment impairment,
- difficulty finding words and solving problems,
- difficulty performing daily activities.

The current strategy for this disease is the delay of symptoms. Today, diagnosis is mainly based on clinical criteria and imaging methods (MRI, PET), which, however, have low sensitivity and detect the disease at advanced stages. The need for non-invasive and sensitive techniques for early biomarker analysis makes mass spectrometry particularly important.

II. Alzheimer's Biomarkers

Biomarkers are molecules detected in biological tissues such as urine, blood, cerebrospinal fluid, etc. They indicate the presence, severity of the disease, as well as the organism's response to treatment.

These biological molecules are analyzed using different advanced techniques, depending on sensitivity, cost, and convenience, in order to determine their concentration in the sample.

The main Alzheimer's biomarkers analyzed by MS are:

A. Amyloid beta protein (A β 1-40, A β 1-42)

- Forms solid extracellular plaques in the brain, affecting normal neuronal function.
- In affected individuals, the A β 42/A β 40 ratio, as a quantitative estimate of plaque formation, is reduced by approximately 14% in CSF and blood plasma compared to healthy individuals, indicating amyloid deposition. [1], [3]

B. Tau protein (P-Tau181, P-Tau217)

- P-Tau181 and P-Tau217 in CSF and blood are the most important forms, as they are directly associated with Alzheimer's disease. Other forms and phosphorylation sites are not always directly related.
- Increased levels of phosphorylated tau (P-tau) constitute a major biomarker of Alzheimer's disease presence.

MS is used for the analysis of both total tau protein in CSF, which provides information on the extent of neurodegeneration, as well as phosphorylated tau, which reflects the presence and extent of neurofibrillary tangles. [1]

III. Mass Spectrometry (MS) Analysis

Mass spectrometry is a process of molecular fragmentation to generate ions for their qualitative and quantitative analysis. Based on the m/z ratio of ions, it identifies the molecules present in the sample and, from peak height and area, determines their quantity. [2]

In analysis, cerebrospinal fluid is mainly used as a sample, since biomarker concentrations are higher there, in contrast to blood where low protein concentrations make results unreliable.

The procedure followed is:

1. Collection of CSF sample from the patient.
2. The sample enters a separation phase such as liquid chromatography (LC) or capillary electrophoresis (CE), where biomolecules are separated.
3. The separated proteins A β 1-40/A β 1-42 or tau enter the nano-ESI ionization source.
4. The sample solution is pumped through a stainless-steel capillary needle at a flow rate of several nL/min.
5. The needle is maintained at a potential of several kV relative to a surrounding cylindrical electrode.
6. Charged droplets are formed, solvent evaporates, and protein molecules become ionized.
7. When charge density reaches the Rayleigh limit, Coulombic fission occurs and droplets split into smaller ones.
8. Multiple charged particles are formed with charges up to +5.
9. The ions enter the mass analyzer, which separates them according to their m/z ratio.
10. The separated ions are converted into an electrical signal and displayed as an m/z spectrum on a computer, representing patient results. [2], [7]

LC-MS/MS analysis of both A β 1-40/A β 1-42 and tau protein facilitates disease diagnosis within a few hours, providing fast and reliable assessment of pathology presence. However, it is not yet established for evaluating disease severity, while studies are ongoing regarding its use in monitoring patient response to therapy.

IV. Conclusions / Perspectives

The behavior of biomarkers during treatment administration is not fully understood. Therefore, mass spectrometry is mainly established for confirming disease presence. It has the ability to detect small biomarker changes and represent them, but these changes do not yet have clear clinical significance. Further studies are required both to understand biomarkers across all disease stages and to develop methods for detecting meaningful changes, with the aim of improving disease management.

V. References

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